

FEATURES OF THE ROLE-PLAYING TO FORM COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS OF LEARNERS

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ANNOTATION

Main goal of the article is to show the importance of using role-playing activities for forming communicative skills of learners, that, there is a general increase in mood, motivation to study the subject, the development of imagination, creativity, the formation of labor, moral education, as well as the development of communication skills.

Key words: *Communication skill, role-play activity, teaching methods, social skills, day-to-day roles, real life situations.*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, education is characterized by an intensive search for a new theory and practice of teaching, new approaches to further improving the content, forms, methods and methods of teaching. This process is due to a number of contradictions, the main of which is the mismatch of traditional methods and forms of training and education with new trends in the development of education. Role-play activity can serve as a valuable teaching and training tool where learners take on different roles, assuming a profile of a character or personality, and interact and participate in diverse and complex learning settings.¹ In the learning process, a role-playing can be considered as a form of organizing a speech situation used for educational purposes.

¹ Ashok A. M. *Effectiveness of Role Play in Enhancing Communication Skills of English Language Learners // Language in India*. - 2015. - T. 15. - No. 4. - Pp. 4-7.

METHODOLOGY

The role-playing is based on an organized speech communication of pupils in accordance with the roles distributed between them. For learners, it is a fascinating activity since even the weakest students are able to take part in it. The great interest of researchers is the use of unconventional, interactive forms and methods in teaching a foreign. That is why it is relevant to consider the use of interactive methods, in particular role play method in teaching oral monological and dialogical speech at early levels of teaching a foreign language.¹

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

In the context of teaching oral foreign language speech, a role-playing is primarily a speech activity, a game and training at the same time. In this regard a role-playing activity from the perspective of the student and teacher might be considered. From the student's point of view, a role-playing is an activity in which they play certain roles. The purpose of the role-playing game is ongoing activities. From the position of a teacher, role-playing can be considered as a form of organization of the educational process, in particular, the process of teaching dialogue. For the teacher, the goal of the game is the formation and development of speech and student skills. The role-playing activity is controllable and its educational nature is clearly recognized by the teacher.

Learners need to learn how to use the target language in "real-life" situations and not structured dialogues which are taught in classroom and role-play like any other task based language teaching technique helps them in language acquisition through real life situations. As Qing states, "Role-play is defined as the projection in real life situations with social activities".² Role-play is an effective technique which, arouses the interest of learners, and makes the language acquisition impressive as Lucantoni points out,

¹ Gorovaya NN *Role play as a method of forming communicative competence in teaching a foreign language // Science and Education*. - 2018. - No. 7 (19). P. 156.

² Qing, X. *Role-play an effective approach to developing overall communicative competence. Cross-Cultural Communication*, 7(4), 37, 2011. P. 37.

“role-play can be a very enjoyable for learners and provide excellent opportunities for using language in real life situations”.¹

Ments comments that role-play are “motivational and effective because it involves activity”. In role-play the participant is asked to play the part of someone else. He is given details about the person and situation that he is supposed to be in. Role-play must not be confused with acting because, unlike acting, role-playing is focused on how the roles of the players interact with and affect each other. Ments also comments that the most obvious uses of role-play are in those areas which deal primarily with aspects of communication. Role-play is a communicative activity where the learners can use spontaneous language. It also helps learners to develop real life speaking skills. Ments also states “by devising scenes of everyday life, in particular those situations which make use of the vocabulary to be learnt, the students can be encouraged to use language in a free and interesting way”². Thus it also helps in developing linguistic competence and also empowers the vocabulary. This enables them to use language in their real life situation in a free and interesting way with confidence.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The use of role-playing methods by teachers in practice may contribute to the implementation of career guidance tasks, and also represents a conditional reproduction by its participants and creates the conditions for real communication. Role play motivates speech activity, as students find themselves in a situation where they need to say something, explain, ask, find out, prove, share something with the interlocutor. What’s more, it activates students' desire for contact with each other and the teacher, creates conditions for equality in speech contact, destroys the traditional barrier between teacher and student.

In a role-playing game, everyone receives a role and should be an active partner in verbal communication. Role-playing gives an opportunity to shy, insecure students

¹ Lucantoni P. *Teaching and assessing skills in English as a second language*. – Cambridge University Press, 2002. P. 44.

² Van Ments M. *The effective use of role-play: Practical techniques for improving learning*. – Kogan Page Publishers, 1999. P. 19.

to speak and thereby overcome the barrier of uncertainty. Conducting role-playing games can contribute to students' conscious learning and ownership of factual material. In addition, they contribute to the development of such qualities as independence, initiative; fostering a sense of collectivism. Students actively, enthusiastically work, help each other, carefully listen to their interlocutors and the teacher only manages the learning activities.¹

Key Benefits of Role-play in English Language Learning:

- to develop communication and language skills;
- to develop social skills when learners collaborate with others and work as a team;
- to encourage a learner to express their ideas and feelings in a relaxed environment created by them;
- to allow a learner to explore, to experiment and to investigate real life situations and language used in various circumstances;
- to build confidence level of team members which in turn can help them in their day-to-day roles;
- to help the students in critical thinking. They can transcend and think beyond the confines of the classroom setting;
- to help them in creative problem-solving and also helps them in handling difficult situation;
- to allow for the interaction between classmates and peers;
- to teach lessons that are needed in society like competition and cooperation;
- to help the introverted students to speak out and it breaks down “cliques” and “isolates”.
- to develop learners’ awareness of themselves and others.²

¹ Safina L.G. *Role-playing games as a way of forming communicative universal educational actions // Modernization of natural science education: teaching methods and practical application: collection of articles of the IV International scientific and practical conference dedicated to the 85th anniversary of the natural-geographical faculty of FSBEI HPE PSGSA. Samara - 2014 . - P. 175.*

² Ashok A. M. *Effectiveness of Role Play in Enhancing Communication Skills of English Language Learners // Language in India. - 2015. - T. 15. - No. 4. - Pp. 4-7.*

Role play is built on interpersonal relationships that are realized in the process of communication, role play causes a need for communication, stimulates interest in participating in communication in a foreign language, and in this case it performs a motivational and incentive function.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, being a model of interpersonal communication, a role-playing method causes the need for communication, the introduction of role-playing activities in the educational process is an important component of the educational process of the learning because in the process of role-play activities, it is possible to realize all the requirements for a modern lesson, namely learners do not receive knowledge in a ready-made form, but they acquire it by joint efforts, and the teacher only directs them.

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